

Austria | One Health Surveillance | *Francisella tularensis*

Background

- Austria recorded a significant rise in cases reported via the mandatory notification system

Objectives

- To investigate the role of vectors like ticks, mosquitoes, and deer flies for the transmission of *F. tularensis*
- To improve information exchange between health authorities

Outcomes & Impact

- By introducing a newly developed questionnaire, we established an improved case assessment process and enabled the rapid transmission of data to our facility for prompt field investigations
- Local health authorities were provided with a practical tool that supports the routine collection of epidemiological data
- 2083 vectors across 6 different locations in Austria were collected. *F. tularensis* was detected in one tick

Lessons learned

- The questionnaire proved to be a valuable tool for gathering information on potential sources of infection and for providing insights relevant to field studies
- Further investigations are needed to understand the role of vectors in the transmission of *F. tularensis*, including other vector groups such as flies

Core messages

- A questionnaire implemented to gather information about cases of tularemia was well accepted by health authorities, as it was used for nearly 50% *F. tularensis* cases reported to the mandatory reporting system.
- Field work revealed one tick carrying *F. tularensis* in regions with human infections. Continuous efforts are needed to identify additional sources of infections with *F. tularensis*, including other groups of arthropods and animal reservoirs.